

A six-membered bimetallic imidazol-4-yl-palladacycle: Synthesis, structure and catalytic activity

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The treatment of 1-methyl-4-iodo-5-phenylthioimidazole (**1**) with Pd(PPh₃)₄ leads to the formation of a six membered bimetallic palladium-imidazol-4-yl complex (**2**). Spectroscopic and crystallographic analysis prove that **2** is made-up of two Pd(PPh₃)₂ unit connected by two C,N-metallated imidazolyl ligand. The six-membered ring adapts a boat shaped conformation. Catalytic activity of **2** towards Suzuki-Miyaura cross coupling of aryl bromides was evaluated and found to be an efficient precatalyst for the coupling of electron rich, sterically hindered and heteroatom containing aryl bromides.

Keywords: NHCs, imidazolyl, bimetallic palladium complex, Suzuki-Miyaura coupling.

Introduction

The strong σ -electron donating capacity, tunable electronic/steric properties and versatile synthetic methodologies have made *N*-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) an impregnable class of ligands in coordination and organometallic chemistry for past three decades with their application being spread across various disciplines like catalysis, medicines and materials¹⁻³. Though most of the reported NHC-metal complexes contains NR,NR type NHC ligands (type A, Chart 1), NHC ligands comprising NR,NH or NH,NH (type B or C, Chart 1) and NR,N (type D, Chart 1) substitution pattern are gaining attention in recent years⁴. Among them, NR,NH and NH,NH substituted NHC ligands (type B and C) are called as protic NHC (*p*NHC) ligands which draws more interest due to the utility of its N-H group in the activation of molecular hydrogen, catalytic hydrogenation and in molecular recognition^{5,6}.

However, metal complexes containing NR,N type ligands (type D), which are also called as imidazolyl-metal complexes have gained less attention over the years despite their novel reactivity^{6e,6f,7}. Generally, they were synthesized by the deprotonation of *N*-alkyl imidazoles/benzimidazoles that are bound to the metal complexes through nitrogen atom⁸. Later, Hahn's group have reported a simple and facile synthesis of imidazol-2-yl-metal complexes through oxidative addition of haloimidazoles with group 10 low valent metal precursors⁹. Recently, they have extended the same procedure to syn-

Chart 1. Metal complexes with NHCs comprising different *N*-substitution pattern.

thesize imidazol-4-yl-platinum complex to be utilized as a precursor for abnormal protic NHC-metal complex^{6a,10}.

Our research group have been working on the synthesis of various backbone functionalized imidazole and imidazolium salts¹¹. Previously, we have reported the synthesis of backbone functionalized normal and abnormal NHC metal complexes containing (NR,NR) type NHC ligands (Chart 2)^{11a-c}. Recently, we have synthesized backbone halo-functionalized imidazol-2-yl (NR,N type) and imidazol-2-ylidene (*n*NHC) metal complexes through facile oxidative addition procedure (Chart 2)¹². The backbone bromo-functionalized NHC-palladium complexes displayed excellent catalytic activity towards challenging electron rich aryl bromides. Based on various tests and careful analysis of

Chart 2. Various backbone functionalized NHC-metal complexes containing NR,NR type *n*NHCs (a)^{11a,c,d}, NR,NR type *a*NHCs (b)^{11b}, NR,N type imidazol-2-yl (c)¹² and NR,N type imidazol-4-yl ligands from our research group.

reaction mixture, a heterogeneous catalytic pathway was proposed where the Pd(0) was reductively eliminated along with phenyl substituted imidazolium salts after the initial transmetalation with phenylboronic acid. The Pd(0) stabilized by the imidazolium salts was believed to be the active catalyst. The backbone bromo-functionalized imidazolyl-palladium complex also showed notable catalytic activity towards cross coupling of aryl bromides. Though there are considerable number of reports on the synthesis of imidazolyl-metal complexes, very few complexes were evaluated for their catalytic activity towards organic transformation^{7b,12,13}. In this work, we report the synthesis of a bimetallic backbone functionalized imidazol-4-yl palladium complex. The catalytic activity of the above complex towards Suzuki-Miyaura coupling of aryl bromides is also reported.

Experimental

Materials and methods:

All the reactions were carried out under an inert atmosphere of nitrogen gas using a standard Schlenk line technique. Glove box was used for sample preparation for reactions. Solvents were dried according to the standard literature procedures and were freshly distilled prior to use. Starting materials such as Pd(PPh₃)₄¹⁴, 1-methyl-4-iodo-5-phenylthioimidazole^{11c} were prepared using the literature procedure. The melting points reported are uncorrected. ¹H, ¹³C and ³¹P NMR spectra were recorded on JEOL (400 MHz)

spectrometers using any one of the solvents such as CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆. The chemical shifts were referenced with respect to TMS (¹H and ¹³C NMR) and 85% H₃PO₄ (³¹P NMR). The ESI mass spectra were recorded on a Waters Q-TOF instrument. IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets using a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum Two FTIR spectrophotometer. Elemental analyses were performed with a Perkin-Elmer Series-II CHNS/O analyzer 2400.

Synthesis of 2:

To a toluene solution (10 mL) of **1** (0.2 mmol, 63.2 mg), was added Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.2 mmol, 231 mg) as solid at 0°C and the mixture was warmed to room temperature and the stirring was continued for 12 h to afford cream colored precipitate. The precipitate was filtered and washed with pentane and diethyl ether thrice and dried in vacuum to give **2**. Slow evaporation of dichloromethane/toluene (5:1) mixture of **2** afforded pale yellow colored crystals suitable for single crystal X-ray diffraction method (Yield: 110 mg, 80%). m.p. 238°C (decomp.). Anal. Calcd. for C₅₆H₄₈I₂N₄P₂Pd₂S₂: C, 49.10; H, 3.53; N, 4.09. Found: C, 48.04; H, 3.56; N, 3.74; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 400 MHz, δ, ppm): 7.94 (s, C2-*H*, 1H), 7.69–7.74 (t, PPh-*H*_{meta}), 7.39–7.42 (t, PPh-*H*_{para}), 7.10–7.26 (m, PPh-*H*_{ortho} + residual toluene protons), 6.96–7.0 (t, SPh-*H*_{para}, 1H), 6.88–6.92 (t, SPh-*H*_{meta}, 2H), 6.53–6.55 (d, SPh-*H*_{para}, 2H), 2.96 (s, N-CH₃, 3H), 2.25 (s, residual Ph-CH₃ protons); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 100 MHz, δ, ppm): 21.5 (PhCH₃ of residual toluene), 32.5 (N-CH₃), 125.4, 125.8, 126.0, 127.9, 128.7, 129.3, 129.4, 130.6, 132.0, 132.6, 135.8, 135.5, 138.9 (phenyl carbons of PPh₃, SPh and residual PhCH₃), 142.5 (C2), 164.2 (C4); ³¹P NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 160 MHz, δ, ppm): 30.4; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3124 (w), 3050 (w), 2924 (w), 1631 (w), 1580 (m), 1511 (vs), 1494 (m), 1477 (s), 1433 (vs), 1411 (m), 1311 (m), 1222 (m), 1184 (w), 1153 (m), 1096 (s), 1024 (w), 998 (w), 973 (w), 795 (w), 749 (vs), 741 (s), 693 (vs), 631 (w), 530 (vs), 510 (s), 467 (w), 438 (w). ESI MS: Found: *m/z* 1370.9075 [M+H]⁺, Calcd. *m/z* 1370.90758.

Procedure for Suzuki-Miyaura coupling:

Aryl bromides (1 mmol), phenylboronic acid (1.2 mmol), cesium carbonate (2.0 mmol), catalyst (0.2 mol%), and DMF (3 mL) were charged in a two neck flask attached with a condenser and the mixture was heated in a oil bath maintained at 80°C for the specified time as given in the Table 3. Then the mixture was diluted with 10 mL water and extracted with 15 mL DCM and filtered over celite. The organic layer

was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, filtered and evaporated to dryness to afford the product. The formation of the products was confirmed by ^1H NMR which matches with the reported values.

X-Ray crystallography:

The crystal data were collected on a Bruker SMART APEX CCD diffractometer. Data were collected using graphite-monochromated MoK_α radiation ($\lambda = 71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 100 K. Using Olex2, the structure was solved using Direct Methods and refined with the SHELXL (2018/3) refinement package using least squares minimization¹⁵. All the hydrogen atoms were included in idealized positions and a riding model was used. Non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters. The CIF and other supplementary information of **2** can be obtained free of charge from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif using CCDC number 1850536.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of **2**:

1-Methyl-4-iodo-5-phenylthioimidazole (**1**) was prepared from 1-methyl-4,5-diiodoimidazole by magnesium-halogen exchange procedure^{11c}. **1** was treated with $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ to undergo oxidative addition reaction to give **2** (Scheme 1). **2** was soluble in dichloromethane and dimethylsulfoxide but poorly soluble in chloroform and other hydrocarbon solvents. The formation of **2** was authenticated by spectroscopic and spectrometric methods. ^1H NMR spectra of **2** shows the symmetrical arrangement of the molecule with a single singlet peak for N- CH_3 proton at 2.95 ppm. A singlet peak at 7.94 ppm corresponds to C2 proton of the imidazole ring and the peaks from 6.53 to 7.51 ppm corresponds to the aryl protons of SPh and PPh_3 groups. The integration of aryl protons denotes the presence of 15 protons for PPh_3 group (1:5 of N- CH_3 : PPh_3) that was coordinated to palladium which confirms the absence of monomeric palladium imidazolyl complex

$[(^{\text{SPh}}\text{Im})\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ which has two PPh_3 groups (30 protons, 1:10 of N- CH_3 : PPh_3) coordinated to palladium¹². ^{13}C NMR spectra shows a peak at 164.2 ppm for metallated C4 carbon. This value is higher than that of the similar palladium-imidazol-2-yl complex (159.5 ppm)^{9a}. ^{31}P NMR of **2** shows a solitary singlet at 30.4 ppm which further affirms the symmetry in the molecule. The formation of bimetallic palladium complex **2** was further confirmed by their ESI-MS peak (1370.9075) which corresponds to the mass of $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ ion and their isotopic distribution pattern matches well with the simulated pattern.

The structure of **2** was explicitly established by single crystal X-ray diffraction method. The crystallographic data are given in Table 1. The crystal structure confirms the presence of bimetallic palladium complex where both the palladium atoms are arranged in a square planar geometry (Fig. 1). Each palladium atom is coordinated to C4 carbon of imidazole ring, iodine, PPh_3 and N3 nitrogen of the second imidazole ring. The six membered palladacycle is arranged in a boat-like conformation. The bond parameters lie in the expected range for similar C2 bound palladium complexes (Table 2). The Pd1-C4 distance is 1.985(7) \AA (Pd1A-C4A) and 2.003(7) \AA (Pd1B-C4B) which is almost equal to the similar C2 bound bimetallic imidazolyl-palladium complex (2.002(3) \AA and 1.988(2) \AA)^{9a}. The Pd-C4 and Pd-I distance of **2** (2.003(7) \AA and 2.6681(7) \AA) is almost similar to the corresponding (NR,NR) type $^{\text{a}}\text{NHC}$ -palladium complex (2.003(4) \AA and 2.6555(5) \AA) reported by our group^{11b}. The bond angles too lie closer with the similar complexes.

Though many C2 bound imidazolyl-metal complexes are known, very few C4 bound imidazolyl-metal complexes were reported. Recently, Hahn has reported a similar six membered bimetallic platinum-imidazolyl complexes. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report of a six membered imidazol-4-yl palladacycle. An attempt to prepare protic $^{\text{a}}\text{NHC}$ -palladium complex by adding NH_4BF_4 to the mixture of **1**

Scheme 1. Synthesis of **2**.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for **2**

2		2	
Empirical formula	C ₅₇ H ₅₀ Cl ₂ I ₂ N ₄ P ₂ Pd ₂ S ₂	$\rho_{\text{calcd.}}$ (g/cm ³)	1.726
Formula wt.	1454.57	μ (mm ⁻¹)	2.014
Crystal system	Triclinic	$F(000)$	1428
Space group	P-1	T (K)	273
a (Å)	10.4564(6)	Refins collected	38453
b (Å)	14.5317(8)	Indep. refins	12219
c (Å)	19.5997(10)	R_{int}	0.0630
α (deg)	105.192	GOOF	1.015
β (deg)	102.003	Data/Restraints/Parameter	12219/0/642
γ (deg)	91.896	R_1/wR_2 [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.0554, 0.1414
V (Å ³)	2799.1(3)	R_1/wR_2 (all data)	0.0928, 0.1631
Z	2		

Fig. 1. **Left:** Molecular structure of **2** (Hydrogens and solvent are omitted for clarity); **Right:** Close view of boat shaped arrangement of palladacycle (Hydrogens and phenyl groups are omitted for clarity).**Table 2.** Selected metric parameters of **2**

Selected bond lengths (Å) of 2					
Pd(1A)-C(4A)	1.985(7)	Pd(1A)-P(2)	2.2662(18)	C(2A)-N(1A)	1.333(8)
Pd(1B)-C(4B)	2.003(7)	Pd(1B)-P(1)	2.2480(18)	C(2A)-N(3A)	1.338(8)
Pd(1A)-N(3B)	2.059(5)	Pd(1B)-I(1B)	2.6681(7)	C(2B)-N(1B)	1.332(8)
Pd(1B)-N(3A)	2.070(5)	C(4A)-C(5A)	1.371(9)	C(2B)-N(3B)	1.312(8)
Pd(1A)-I(1A)	2.6793(7)	C(4B)-C(5B)	1.357(9)	N(3A)-C(4A)	1.379(8)
N(1B)-C(5B)	1.399(8)	N(1A)-C(5A)	1.400(8)	N(3B)-C(4B)	1.392(8)
Selected bond angles (°) of 2					
N(1A)-C(2A)-N(3A)	110.7(6)	C(4B)-Pd(1B)-N(3A)	84.2(2)	C(4A)-Pd(1A)-P(2)	91.46(19)
N(1B)-C(2B)-N(3B)	112.0(6)	C(4B)-Pd(1B)-P(1)	95.68(19)	N(3A)-Pd(1B)-P(1)	168.49(16)
C(2A)-N(3A)-C(4A)	108.0(6)	N(2B)-Pd(1A)-P(2)	172.70(16)	C(4B)-Pd(1B)-I(1B)	170.65(19)
C(2B)-N(3B)-C(4B)	107.3(5)	C(4A)-Pd(1A)-I(1A)	167.68(18)	N(3A)-Pd(1B)-I(1B)	90.26(15)

and Pd(PPh₃)₄ in toluene at 100°C was unsuccessful. This might be due to the stability factor of protic NHCs, which needs wider optimization of solvent and temperature.

Catalysis:

As mentioned earlier, the catalytic activity of imidazolyl-palladium complexes are less explored. In this study, catalytic activity of **2** towards Suzuki-Miyaura cross coupling of aryl bromides with phenylboronic acid was evaluated. The reaction was carried out in DMF (solvent) in the presence of Cs₂CO₃ (base) at 80°C. Various aryl bromides containing electron withdrawing group, electron donating group and heteroatom were used as substrates to couple with phenylboronic acid. The progress of the reactions was monitored by GC-MS.

Apart from catalyzing the coupling of 4-bromobenzaldehyde and bromobenzene in just 3 h with quantitative yield (Table 3, entry 1 and 2), the precatalyst **2** displayed excellent activity even with challenging electron rich substrate like

4-bromotoluene with 96% yield in 6 h with just 0.2 mol% precatalyst loading (entry 3). More interestingly, **2** effectively catalyzed the coupling of both electron rich and sterically encumbered substrate 2-bromomesitylene in excellent yield (Table 3, entry 4). The performance of **2** with 4-bromoanisole is slightly lower than the above substrates (entry 5). In the case of heteroatom containing aryl bromides, **2** displayed excellent activity with 2-bromothiophene with quantitative yield in just 3 h (entry 6) but the activity is poorer with 2-bromopyridine yielding just 23% (entry 7).

The conversion of the products was monitored by GC-MS and the yields were calculated from ¹H NMR spectrum of the crude reaction mixtures with reference to the ratio of unreacted aryl bromides and the product (Supporting information). The isolated yield of the pure product, TON and TOF are given in Table 3. The formation of dark palladium particles was observed during the catalysis. The activity of the catalyst is found to be sluggish over the time (after 3 h).

Table 3. Catalytic activity of **2** towards Suzuki-Miyaura coupling reactions^a

Entry	Ar-Br	Time (h)	Cat. loading (mol%)	Product	Yield (%)		TON ^d	TOF ^e (h ⁻¹)
					NMR yield ^b	Isolated yield		
1		100	96	480	160			
2		100	94	470	156			
3		99	94	470	78			
4		96	92	230	29			
5		77	71	355	44			
6		100	93	465	155			
7		23 ^c	17	86	11			

^aReaction conditions: aryl halide (1 mmol), PhB(OH)₂ (1.2 mmol), Cs₂CO₃ (2.0 mmol) and DMF (3 mL). ^bNMR yield (yield calculated from the NMR spectrum of crude mixture with reference to the unreacted aryl bromides). ^cGC yield. ^dTON = moles of product/moles of cat.. ^eTOF = TON/time (h).

These observations suggest that the reaction might progress through the heterogenous pathway, however, detailed study of the palladium particles and the reaction mixture is necessary to arrive at a conclusion which is now under progress. The bimetallic imidazolyl-palladium complex **2** displayed better catalytic activity than the monomeric imidazol-2-yl-palladium complexes reported by our group¹².

Conclusions

A six membered bimetallic imidazol-4-yl palladium-imidazolyl complex (**2**) was prepared by simple and facile oxidative addition of 1-methyl-4-iodo-5-phenylthioimidazole (**1**). The complex was completely characterized by spectroscopic, spectrometric and crystallographic methods. **2** features bimetallic palladium atoms with square planar geometry. The six membered palladacycle was arranged in boat shaped conformation. The catalytic activity of **2** was explored for Suzuki-Miyaura coupling of aryl bromides with boronic acid. **2** displayed excellent activity even with challenging electron rich and sterically hindered substrates. The formation of dark palladium particles during the catalysis hinted the possibility of heterogeneous pathway which needs further analysis of the reaction mixture. The study of reaction pathway and the extension of this methodology to synthesize 3d metal-complexes of various functionalized imidazolyl ligands are under progress.

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Supporting information

The Supporting information contains NMR spectra of compound **2** and crude products of the catalysis.

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